

ASAP

A Systemic APProach to social media
and pre-adolescents through thinking

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME

IMPACT EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

Co-funded by
the European Union

IMPACT EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

www.socialmediakids.eu | [Erasmus+ Project Results Platform](#) project page | [Zenodo](#) project community page

R4.1.2 ASAP Impact Evaluation Framework

August 2025

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The ASAP project is co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043. The support of the European Commission and of the Italian National Agency INDIRE to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of its content, which reflects the views of the authors only. The European Commission and the Italian National Agency INDIRE shall not be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained herein.

Licence

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#) licence, allowing for the use, distribution, and modification of the work, including commercially, as long as proper attribution is given to the original creators and any changes are indicated.

You may be required to clear additional rights if a specific content includes third-party works or depicts identifiable private individuals. To use or reproduce content that is not owned by the creators of this work, you may need to seek permission directly from the right holders.

Contents

- Introduction..... 4
- Observation grid..... 5
- Questionnaire..... 7
- Using the Framework in Practice 10
- Interpreting the Results..... 11
- Limitations and Opportunities 12
- Conclusion 13

ASAP Educational Programme Handbook

Impact Evaluation Framework

INTRODUCTION

The ASAP Impact Evaluation Framework was developed to provide a clear, flexible and comparable tool to analyse the outcomes and changes generated by the ASAP Educational Programme among its learners, particularly preadolescents. Its purpose is not only to measure whether specific objectives have been achieved, but above all to understand how and to what extent learners' competences, behaviours, and relational dynamics have changed throughout the Learning Units.

The framework is structured around four transversal competence areas that underpin the ASAP Educational Programme and inform both its educational design and impact evaluation:

- Personal competence (e.g. self-awareness, emotional literacy, autonomy);
- Social competences (e.g., collaboration, empathy, conflict management);
- Learning-to-learn competences (e.g. metacognitive awareness, self-regulation, reflective skills);
- Digital competences (e.g., online behaviour, identity, and data awareness).

To ensure reliability, the tool is adaptable to the number and type of Learning Units of the ASAP Educational Programme implemented in each educational setting. Indicators can be selected or organised per Learning Unit, keeping the number of items intentionally limited to avoid response saturation and to ensure meaningful variability in participants' answers.

The model integrates two complementary instruments: an Observation Grid, designed to monitor group processes and participation, and a Questionnaire, aimed at capturing individual perceptions and levels of awareness at three key stages (T0, T1, T2). This combined approach provides both a transversal view of group dynamics and a focused analysis of individual development, enabling educators to identify immediate changes as well as longer-term effects.

OBSERVATION GRID

The Observation Grid is a qualitative tool completed by educators at the beginning (T0) and at the end (T2) of the learning pathway. It is designed to capture how the group functions, evolves and engages throughout the Learning Units. Rather than providing a rigid set of indicators, the tool offers a flexible framework that can be adapted to the specific characteristics of each group and to the focus of the Learning Units implemented.

Educators are invited to observe behaviours, interactions and relational dynamics reflecting the four transversal competence areas addressed by ASAP: personal competences, social competences, learning-to-learn competences and digital competences. Observations can be recorded using a numerical scale (e.g. 1–5) or through descriptive notes, depending on the level of detail required.

Below is a suggested set of core indicators, intended as a starting point for observation:

Suggested indicators

- Listening and attention: the extent to which participants listen to one another and remain focused during discussions and activities.
- Respect for turn-taking: the ability to speak in turns without interrupting peers.
- Relevance of contributions: the degree to which participants' comments and ideas are connected to the topic or activity.
- Balanced participation: the extent to which all group members feel included and are actively involved.
- Collaboration and cooperation: the ability to work together, share tasks and support peers.
- Conflict management: how disagreements are addressed and whether the group is able to reach shared solutions.
- Emotional awareness and self-expression: participants' ability to recognise and express emotions appropriately within group interactions.
- Initiative and autonomy: participants' willingness to propose ideas, ask questions and take responsibility within activities.
- Use of digital tools (where applicable): how participants interact with digital content, demonstrate awareness of online behaviour and apply concepts related to digital responsibility.

Educators may adapt, add or replace indicators according to the group's needs, the characteristics of the educational context and the specific Learning Units implemented. For example, Learning Units focused on emotional awareness may require closer attention to emotional expression and self-regulation, while those addressing digital identity may emphasise online behaviour, identity construction or data awareness.

The purpose of the Observation Grid is not to assess or judge individual performance, but to offer a structured yet flexible framework for understanding group dynamics and supporting educators in interpreting the changes that emerge throughout the learning pathway.

Indicator	Observation focus	Rating (1–5)	Qualitative notes / Evidence
Listening and attention	Participants listen to peers, follow instructions and remain focused during discussions and activities	4	Good attention overall; occasional loss of focus during whole-group discussions
Balanced participation	All group members are able to participate, without persistent domination or withdrawal	3	Most participants contribute spontaneously; two require encouragement to take part
Collaboration	Participants cooperate effectively, share tasks and provide support to peers during group activities	5	Effective cooperation during group tasks; spontaneous peer support observed.
Conflict management	Disagreements emerge and are managed constructively, either autonomously by the group or with educator support	2	Tension observed during decision-making; educator mediation required to resolve disagreements.
Use of digital tools (if applicable)	Participants use digital tools and content responsibly, showing awareness of appropriate online behaviour	4	Appropriate awareness of digital responsibility; participants seek consent before sharing or recording.
...			

QUESTIONNAIRE

The Questionnaire is administered individually to participants at three stages (T0, T1 and T2) to assess the development of competences, awareness, attitudes and behaviours influenced by the Learning Units. It uses a 1–5 Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree) and is designed to capture changes reflecting the impact of the activities on participants' ways of thinking, relating and acting in their everyday lives, both online and offline.

To ensure meaningful variability and avoid response saturation or overly homogeneous answers, the questionnaire includes a limited and carefully selected number of statements. Educators may choose the items that best reflect the Learning Units implemented, ideally selecting between four and six statements per Learning Unit. Additional items may be added or adapted, provided that they remain aligned with the competences and educational objectives addressed by the Learning Units.

The suggested statements below are organised by Learning Unit and aim to assess the competences targeted by the activities, rather than participants' recall or memorisation of content. They may be used as provided or complemented with additional statements that remain consistent with the pedagogical focus of each Learning Unit.

Learning Unit: Emotions

1. I can recognise what I am feeling before I react.
2. When I feel strong emotions, I can pause and try to understand them.
3. I can often understand how someone else feels from their expressions or behaviour.
4. Sometimes I confuse one emotion with another. (reverse-coded)
5. When I talk about my feelings, I can choose words that describe them well.
6. I find it difficult to notice how my emotions influence my actions. (reverse-coded)

Learning Unit: The Power of Questions

1. I can ask questions that help me understand others better.
2. When something is unclear, I feel comfortable asking for more information.
3. I can ask questions that open up a conversation rather than close it.
4. Sometimes I hold back my questions even when I need them to understand. (reverse-coded)
5. I can explain the difference between asking questions to get information and asking questions to explore ideas.
6. I can listen carefully to answers and ask a follow-up question.

Learning Unit: Communication

1. I can express my ideas clearly so that others can understand them.
2. I can listen without interrupting, even when I disagree.
3. I can explain my point of view without hurting or attacking others.
4. Sometimes I misunderstand what others mean, especially in online communication. (reverse-coded)
5. I can adapt the way I communicate depending on who I am talking to.

- I can ask for clarification when I feel confused during a conversation.

Learning Unit: Authenticity and Authority

- I can recognise when online content may not show the whole truth.
- Before trusting something online, I stop and think about where it comes from.
- I can notice when a photo or video looks edited, altered or exaggerated.
- Sometimes I believe things online too quickly without checking. (reverse-coded)
- I can decide whether an online message deserves my attention.
- I can explain why it is important to understand who created an online post and for what purpose.

Learning Unit: Onlife

- I think about possible consequences before posting or sharing something online.
- I can tell the difference between what is safe to share and what should stay private.
- Sometimes I forget that my online actions can have effects offline. (reverse-coded)
- I can recognise when I need to take a break from digital devices.
- I can choose how to use digital media in a way that reflects my values.
- I can follow shared digital agreements that protect everyone’s wellbeing.

Learning Unit: Role Models

- I can recognise which values matter to me when I look at people I admire.
- I can notice when an influencer’s content makes me compare myself negatively.
- I can decide independently whether a viral trend is safe or appropriate for me.
- I understand that what I see online does not always reflect real life.
- I can choose role models who help me grow rather than those who put pressure on me.
- I can recognise when a challenge or trend goes against my values or wellbeing.

Below is an example of the questionnaire table to be completed individually.

How much do you agree with the following statements?

Please use the scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). There are no right or wrong answers. Please answer honestly.

Emotions	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neither agree nor disagree	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
I can recognise what I am feeling before I react.					
When I feel strong emotions, I can pause and try to understand them.					

Emotions	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neither agree nor disagree	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
I can often understand how someone else feels from their expressions or behaviour.					
Sometimes I confuse one emotion with another.					
When I talk about my feelings, I can choose words that describe them well.					
I find it difficult to notice how my emotions influence my actions.					

USING THE FRAMEWORK IN PRACTICE

The Impact Evaluation Framework is designed to be used flexibly across a wide range of educational settings, while maintaining coherence with the core principles of the ASAP Educational Programme. Its structure allows educators to adapt the tools to the rhythm, dynamics and logistical constraints of their groups, without compromising the quality or comparability of the data collected.

In practice, educators may select the most appropriate approaches for administering questionnaires and conducting observations. Data may be collected individually, in small groups or at whole-class level, depending on the objectives of the implementation. Observations can take place during activities, transitions or debriefing moments, or through guided prompts designed to elicit specific behaviours or attitudes aligned with the Learning Units.

Self-assessment questionnaires may be administered either digitally or on paper. Where appropriate, anonymity should be ensured in order to reduce social desirability bias. Item selection should remain intentional and limited, focusing on the competences most relevant to the Learning Units that were actually implemented. Educators are encouraged to complement quantitative data with brief qualitative notes, which often provide essential context for interpreting behaviours and attitudes.

The framework is not intended to generate rigid metrics or high-stakes results. Rather, it functions as a pedagogical support tool that fosters reflection and enables educational teams to plan, adjust and consolidate learning pathways. When used consistently over time, it can reveal meaningful patterns that help educators refine their strategies and better understand how preadolescents engage with the key messages of the ASAP Educational Programme.

Importantly, the framework reflects a broader educational stance. Rather than supporting one-off or isolated interventions, it emphasises the importance of continuity in educational work and in reflective monitoring over time. Meaningful change in competences, attitudes and behaviours, particularly in the digital, emotional and relational domains addressed by the ASAP Educational Programme, emerges through sustained and coherent learning pathways, not through single activities. In this sense, evaluation becomes a tool for accompanying educational processes, reinforcing continuity and supporting long-term educational impact.

INTERPRETING THE RESULTS

Interpreting the results requires a reflective and context-sensitive approach. Individual scores and isolated data points should not be interpreted as definitive judgments, but rather as indicators of tendencies, emerging competences and developmental processes. In this perspective, comparisons across T0, T1 and T2 are particularly meaningful, as they highlight not only immediate changes but also processes of consolidation or regression over time, helping educators to understand which aspects of learning have become internalised.

When analysing the results, educators are encouraged to look for patterns across the different tools used. For example, an increase in a participant's confidence or critical awareness reported in the questionnaire may be reinforced or nuanced by observational evidence related to group participation or communicative behaviour. Conversely, apparent inconsistencies between tools can provide valuable insights into the complexity of preadolescents' developmental trajectories.

Interpretation should also take into account contextual factors, such as school culture, group cohesion, prior experiences with digital media or family attitudes towards technology and communication. These variables influence how competences are expressed and should therefore be considered when drawing conclusions or planning follow-up actions.

Rather than aiming for standardised benchmarks, the purpose of the framework is to generate meaningful insights that support educational decision-making. When analysed thoughtfully, the data can inform future planning, identify areas requiring further reinforcement and deepen educators' understanding of how young people internalise the objectives of the ASAP Learning Units.

LIMITATIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Like all educational evaluation tools, this framework presents inherent limitations that should be acknowledged to ensure responsible interpretation. Self-assessment data may be influenced by social desirability, momentary emotional states or levels of metacognitive awareness typical of preadolescence. Observational data, while rich and contextualised, are inevitably shaped by the educator's perspective, group composition and situational factors that may affect participation during specific sessions.

These limitations, however, do not diminish the value of the framework. On the contrary, they highlight the importance of approaching evaluation as a dynamic and interpretative process. When analysed thoughtfully and complemented by qualitative insights, the data can offer meaningful opportunities to understand learning trajectories, identify strengths and areas for development, and adapt pedagogical strategies more effectively.

The open and adaptable design of the framework represents a further strength. Schools and organisations may expand the set of indicators, integrate additional tools (some of which are already suggested or embedded within specific Learning Units), such as reflective journals, peer observation or focus group discussions, or align the evaluation process with existing institutional practices. This flexibility makes the framework suitable for diverse educational contexts and responsive to the evolving digital, emotional and social experiences of young people.

CONCLUSION

The ASAP Impact Evaluation Framework provides a coherent and flexible structure for understanding how the Learning Units contribute to the development of competences among learners. By combining educators' observations with participants' self-assessments collected at different stages (T0, T1 and T2), the framework offers a multidimensional view of the changes occurring both at group level and in individual awareness, attitudes and behaviours.

The evaluation is not intended to measure the memorisation of content, but rather to capture how participants learn to recognise emotions, ask meaningful questions, distinguish reliable information, reflect on their digital presence, communicate in balanced and respectful ways, and relate critically to role models. For this reason, the proposed indicators and questionnaire items should be understood as examples that can be adapted and expanded according to the Learning Units implemented and the specific characteristics of each group. This open and modular approach is intentional, as it reflects the nature of the ASAP Handbook itself, which is conceived as a flexible and adaptable resource designed to be used across diverse educational contexts and to respond to the needs of different learning environments.

Within this perspective, evaluation becomes an integral part of the learning process. It supports reflection, makes progress visible and enables educators to identify emerging needs and refine their pedagogical choices. By valuing both learning processes and competence development, the framework strengthens the overall impact of the ASAP Educational Programme and contributes to guiding young people towards a more aware, autonomous and responsible onlife experience.

www.socialmediakids.eu

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME